

Evidence that background reddish dots in the background of the image of Galaxy Glass-z13 are Extremely redshifted far off Galaxies

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Abstract

The background in the image of Galaxy Glass-z13 is filled with innumerable small red dots. This short article presents a proof that these small dots are far off and extremely red shifted galaxies.

Article:

image credit: NASA/STScI/GLASS-JWST program: R. Naidu, G. Brammer, T. Treu. - Image source: EarthSky | Oldest galaxy yet seen by Webb Telescope (image source) Credits source: Did JWST find the most distant galaxy ever seen? Maaaaaybe.

Above is image of galaxy Glass-z13. In the center of the image, the red galaxy is Glass-z13 which is officially a candidate for the title of most distant observed galaxy. This galaxy is seen in this image "as existed almost very close to the time of big bang".

In the same image, there are innumerable small red dots. This article will show that these are also galaxies and these visible galaxies are located very far away that even scientists ignored them. **They are seen in this image as located away from the timeframe of the big bang. That means actually there was no big bang.**

To say that these innumerable small reddish dots in this image are galaxies requires to be supported by reasonable and sufficient evidence. The researchers who discovered the galaxy Glass-z13 have not denied the existence of small reddish dots as they have just discussed "two particularly luminous sources" which they present as galaxies Glass-z13 and Glass-z11 respectively in their paper.ⁱ Seems like luminous sources below certain level were of no interest to them and they did not discuss them in detail. Anyhow, if small reddish dots in the background of galaxy Glass-z13 are mere distortion of the image and not real in the sense of massive objects then it is another question on the quality of the images of JWST. Fortunately we have indications that these smaller red dots are in fact galaxies. Well, simple red dots, if these are merely visible dots and nothing else, cannot be magnified through the gravity lensing of the foreground galaxies. In the following images which are all different portions of the JWST's first deep image and have been presented in a report about the discovery of a type of Einstein Cross with six image system of lensed galaxies,ⁱⁱ the individual small dots (The same things as visible in Glass-z13 image) have been magnified and repeated six times through gravitational lensing of the foreground galaxies.

In short, in the JWST images, there is huge population of small reddish dots. These dots are so small that researches simply treated them like luminous sources below certain level and thus not important for their research. They just took a far bigger red dot as a candidate for the most distant observed galaxy. According to them that most distant galaxy is also like nearer most to the big bang.

However, the huge population of smaller background red dots has been hugely taken up by the intervening magnifying foreground galaxies such that the "foreground" galaxies are also actually very distant galaxies. The huge number of six image systems of Einstein Crossⁱⁱⁱ in the JWST deep image is simply due to the reason that there are huge number of very small looking background galaxies which are located at distances which should be at least three times away from Earth than the distance of our subject candidate galaxy for the title of "most distant observed galaxy" i.e. Glass-z13.

ⁱ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2207.09434.pdf>

ⁱⁱ <https://zenodo.org/record/6951376#.Yuu-1VxBzct>

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